

UNDERSTANDING THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF DEFENSE OF THE ANCIENTS (DOTA) PLAYER: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL INQUIRY

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Understanding the Lived Experiences of Defense of the Ancients (DOTA) Player: A Phenomenological Inquiry

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Abstract

The purpose of this hermeneutic phenomenological inquiry was to explore and understand the Lived experiences of the five specified Defense of the Ancients (DOTA) Players of Fatima National High School, North Fatima District, Division of General Santos City. The participants underwent one-on-one, in-depth interviews to gain knowledge and more understanding of the phenomenon. The focus of the study, which is interpretive, is on the richness of their personal views and feelings and their impact on their experiences as DOTA players. It utilized the thematic analysis approach through the coded method in analyzing data. This research expedition revealed that being hooked on DOTA gaming created both positive and negative impacts on the participants. The interview data yields the following themes: Strengthen Social Connections, Recreational Therapy and Coping Mechanism and Aptitude Enrichment, Adrenalin Rush, Positive feelings, Negative feelings, Develop Inferiority Complex, Health risk, Effects on Academic Performance, Effects on plans, Effects on the relationship with family or loved ones. Furthermore, the result exposed that playing DOTA has numerous effects on the part of the Player. Hence, nowadays, learner/s are so fond and hooked to DOTA gaming, notwithstanding the fact that their Academic, Social, Family, and Personal lives have been strongly affected and shaped by these new advancements in technology like video games with their virtual reality environments.

Keywords: *educational management, lived experiences, dota gaming, defense of the ancients player, phenomenology, philippines*

Introduction

The rapid advancement and widespread adoption of information technology, communication, and entertainment tools have made new technological innovations and social applications readily accessible. Among these developments, video gaming has particularly captivated many young people. The proliferation of high-tech devices and the growing popularity of the internet have elevated digital gaming to a prominent activity, especially among adolescents. Millennials, often referred to as “digital natives,” grew up during this era of rapid technological advancement with the extensive use of ICTs for communication and information in various aspects of daily life (Abbasi, et al., 2022; Yongsung & Circella, 2019).

Undoubtedly, Gaming is one of the most extensive recreational activities regardless of culture, age, and gender, especially since the development of the internet. Games. Playing games has become a mainstream pastime, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic; recent research released by Nielsen found that video gaming is at an all-time high (White, 2020; Nielsen, 2020).

Additionally, Facebook groups related to DOTA have gained popularity, underscoring the impact of parental supervision and parent-child relationships on teenage internet addiction. Many young Filipinos actively participate in public groups, such as "Ibagsak ang Edukasyon, Ipang-DOTA ang baon!" These groups often share images and content that go viral online. This highlights the complex interaction between parental influence (Bradt, et al., 2023; Daisuki, et al., 2024)

In particular, the viral nature of online content, and the prevalence of gambling behaviors among youth, Participant 1 confessed to the researcher in a one-on-one in-depth interview that he began and started to commit crimes like stealing his neighbor’s pet to have some money to spend on DOTA gaming. Thus, the game is the source of a growing gambling and stealing problem among local youths. In Fatima National High School, just like any other school here in General Santos City, most of the students, especially in their Senior high school, are also attracted to and hooked on this game because of its popularity (Pranata, 2021).

Most of them testify to their friends that it is worth playing for. Others even teach their friends and promote the game. Though it is easy to learn, fun to play, and user-friendly yet, there are numerous unpleasant effects evident on the part of the players, particularly with the five (5) specified respondents in Senior high School Grade 12 EIM learners, according to Naoto Kan, Japan’s Prime Minister (Naoto Kan, 2011). “It is impossible to solve a problem if you do not understand its root cause. Yes, true indeed; how can we fight and face our invisible enemy (Naoto Kan, 2011)?

In other words, before we can fix a problem, we must first determine what it is and devote significant thought and resources to comprehending it. Because today's problems are more complex, we know already that they cannot be solved by being broken down into specific components, the same as what Albert Einstein stressed, that if “Given "I would spend 55 minutes to save the world in an hour." identifying the problem and 5 minutes finding a solution.” I genuinely agree with both of these great minds on how to solve a problem that was unknown to us. We should first learn to identify what the problem really is before finding its solutions.

Aside from this, What happens if no one understands and understands the problem? When the problem is not well defined and

understood, well, probably, “solutions” will be ineffective, and it will only create new problems. In fact, there is no guarantee that the solutions will address the problem at all. To such a degree, the more we understand the problem, the more likely we are to understand the root cause, and we could probably create countermeasures so the problem would not recur.

Similar to what the researchers hoped and aimed for in conducting this study, due to the fact that most teenagers today are living in technologically sophisticated times, which may be beneficial for their development, many students in their senior high school are stuck in a technologically addicted state. This problem is evident in the real world of students at Fatima National High School, where many of them miss school, arrive late, and engage in other disruptive behaviors that make it difficult for them to meet the most basic learning competencies set by the Department of Education.

One participant in the study shared a personal experience illustrating the consequences of DOTA addiction. He admitted that his addiction led him to commit theft, resulting in criminal charges and complaints from his neighbor, who was the victim. He expressed deep regret and disbelief over his actions, which damaged his reputation and caused significant turmoil. The incident also contributed to violence, harmful gossip, gambling, disputes, and other problems within the community. This personal account was a substantial motivator for conducting the study, as it was closely related to my eldest son, which profoundly influenced my interest in this research to understand and dig deeper into the root cause. This study aimed to explore the reasons.

In addition, behind the effects of alarming video gaming addiction, specifically focusing on how and why individuals become hooked on games like Defense of the Ancients (DOTA). It sought to understand the underlying causes of such uncontrollable behavior. As a Senior High School teacher, I observed firsthand the impact of DOTA addiction on students. The addictive behavior was evident through classroom anecdotal notes and students’ progress reports, including issues such as cutting classes, tardiness, and absenteeism. These observations underscored the need to address and understand this addiction more deeply.

Such led the researcher to examine further and be intrigued by this game-hooked state and this problem involving her EIM 12 advisory class, which, to her, remains unresolved. Besides, the Reviewed literature showed that no studies are presently investigating the lived experiences of Fatima National High School (DOTA) Players. Thus, there needs to be more Context Knowledge and a need for further study.

Research Questions

1. How do the participants view and describe their experiences as DOTA players?
 - 1.1 How do the participants view their experiences with DOTA gaming?
 - 1.2 How do the participants feel about their experiences with DOTA and gaming?
 - 1.3 How does DOTA gaming affect their lives?

Methodology

This section presented the study's methodology, including the research design, the role of the researcher, the research participants, data collection, data analysis, trustworthiness, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study was qualitative in approach, phenomenological in tradition, hermeneutic in discipline, and interpretive in interpretation. It utilized approaches to answer the research questions in this study as it aimed to assist the researcher in gaining an in-depth view of the Defense of the Ancients players’ experiences. The questions assumed a focus on how the participant respondents interpret their experience, how they view themselves, and how they understand the phenomenon. Qualitative research technique was utilized in the process of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting non-numerical data in this paper (Maxwell & Rebold, 2015).

Additionally, it was used as an effective tool to understand how the participants subjectively perceive; and give meaning to their social reality; it used an inquiry approach wherein the researcher investigates the central phenomenon by asking participants broad and general questions in gathering elaborated views through words, scrutinized data for descriptions and themes, interprets the meaning of the information collected based on personal reflections on previous research and encodes final reports which do not include personal biases. Qualitative research is a broad term covering different data gathering and analytical approaches to provide an appropriate explanation (Tsang, 2023).

Thus, it is an interpretation of the social phenomenon, it also responded to the questions about experience, meaning, and perception, most often from the participant’s viewpoint. This research used the Phenomenological design, which was constructed to gather information about present existing conditions. It involved the collection of data about the current status of the subject under study, which measured the existing phenomenon. The term "phenomenology" refers to what appears to us and is "derived from the Greek word "phenomenon," which is the present participle of the verb "phainesthai," to appear. Qualitative research methods such as phenomenology have their roots in psychology and philosophy, and they explore the experiences of those living with a particular phenomenon (Jackson, 2021).

Further, this leads the researcher to gain a complete and deep understanding of the experience as conveyed by the person living the

experience firsthand. Specifically, the phenomenology of hermeneutics in a discipline with basic themes such as interpretation, textual meaning, dialogue, pre-understanding, and tradition will be utilized in this research. Hermeneutic phenomenology is interested in the subjective experience of persons or groups with an attempt to discover the world as experienced by the participants through their own stories. Besides, this study was supported by combining hermeneutic analysis with other methods of analysis that aim to interpret and understand meanings; it also supports the idea that description itself is an interpretive procedure and that hermeneutics can offer the best interpretation of a phenomenon. Hermeneutical phenomenology relies on both interpretation and description of the lived experience (Jackson, 2021; Aco, 2023).

Hence, It was a descriptive (phenomenological) methodology because it was attentive to how things appear; it wanted to let things speak for themselves. As it maintains that there are no uninterpreted phenomena, it is an interpretive hermeneutic methodology. The term "qualitative research" is broad and encompasses several data-gathering and analytical approaches to provide a cultural and appropriate explanation and interpretation of the social phenomenon. Thus, it responded to the questions about experience, meaning, and perception, most often from the participant's viewpoint (Van Manen, 2014; Alforon, 2019).

Moreover, this research used the Phenomenological design, which was constructed to gather information about present existing conditions. It involved the collection of data about the current status of the subject under study, which measured the existing phenomenon (Alforon, 2019).

In this study, the main objective of phenomenological research is to obtain complex and clear descriptions of human experiences. Generally speaking, qualitative research is usually described as Phenomenological in approach, hermeneutic in tradition, and interpretative in analysis, which focuses on the exploration and logical interpretation of the phenomena from within, and its starting point is the taking of the perspectives and shared experiences of research participants, through careful exploration, I seek firsthand information to gain an understanding of events through the lens of the participant. It is a method of naturalistic investigation that aims to comprehend social phenomena in-depth in their natural environments. It depends on firsthand accounts of social phenomena and concentrates on the "why and how" as opposed to the "what" and how" rather than the "what" of social phenomena (Jimenez, et al., 2022; Cutler, et al., 2021).

Eventually, It relies on the direct experiences of participants in their everyday lives. Rather than by logical and statistical procedures, this qualitative research was situated as an activity that locates and directs the world's watcher. It is made up of a variety of material and interpretive acts that bring the world to life. These actions change the world. Through the use of field notes, interviews, conversations, photos, recordings, and memos to oneself, they transform the world into a series of representations. This degree of qualitative research takes a naturalistic, interpretive stance toward the world. Accordingly, qualitative researchers investigate phenomena in their natural environments, seeking to explain or interpret events in terms of the meanings that individuals assign to them (Lanka, et al., 2021; Pietkiewicz & Smith, 2012).

Further, this study, which took a hermeneutics phenomenology approach, utilized data collection procedures such as in-depth interviews, semi-structured interviews, and unconstructive interviews. It sought to reveal the meaning and principal structures or essences of participants' lived experience with a phenomenon, and the researcher chose a Phenomenological design (Oerther, 2021; Jackson, 2021).

Thus, this study employed a Hermeneutic Phenomenological approach to comprehend the situations in which people have lived fully. The researcher believed that a hermeneutic approach was essential not only to describe but also to interpret the phenomenon in question. Conducting in-depth interviews served the following purposes: explore and appreciate the participants' actual experiences rather than predict, control, or manipulate those experiences (Jackson, 2021).

Indeed, Both the Phenomenological approach and the hermeneutic tradition involve interpretive analysis, which includes a detailed examination of personal accounts and their presentation. A discussion of the common experiential themes is paired with the researcher's interpretation, which is a double hermeneutics in nature. This study applied a detailed understanding of theoretical and practical aspects of qualitative survey, interviewing, and participant description, followed by a discussion of the analysis of qualitative data and problems with the quality, portability, and application of qualitative research. Qualitative data is defined as non-numerical data, such as text, video, photographs, or audio recordings (Oerther, 2021)

Hence, In this study, there are five specified participants of learners at Fatima National High School who described their lived experiences; this type of data was collected using in-depth interviews and analyzed and scrutinized data through thematic analysis; the researcher analyzed their accounts, uncovered similar themes that the participants discussed to learn new information and understanding about living through a particular phenomenon or life experience.

Actually, the identified patterns were present in all texts and served to deepen the meaning of the phenomenon as understood by the researcher. Phenomenology requires us to view things through a lens that shows them (things, experiences) as they indeed are so that we gain a proper understanding of them. I viewed research strategy as an active process that involved decision-making based on detailed responses of the participants to the research questions asked. As the research progresses, there are possible changes that may occur that need to be embedded in the transcriptions for the purpose of meeting better. (Alforon, 2019).

And more reliable outcomes that could enlighten the researcher and those who could benefit from this study (Alfornon, 2019).

Participants

Deliberately, there were five specified critical informants in this study. They were all Defense of the Ancients Players and are all Grade 12 students of Fatima National High School for the school year 2019-2020. They are residents of Barangay Fatima, Uhaw, General Santos City. The Participants were coded to maintain confidentiality and anonymity; they were selected as respondents of this study because of their experiences that are related to the focus of the analysis, which is interpretive, on the richness of the personal views and experiences of the specified participants.

Indeed, to develop rich and comprehensive understandings about people, particularly young adolescents who are currently hooked on DOTA gaming. I was able to collect relevant data directly from the Defense of the Ancient Players, who were the informants, after conducting a one-on-one interview. I then proceeded to transcribe and analyze all the data gathered from the in-depth interviews. A formal analysis of the collected information was done based on the suggestions (Ravindran, 2019).

However, in order to maintain the confidentiality of the participants, it utilized codes assigned to identify the DOTA player participants (Ravindran, 2019).

Data Analysis

Indeed, in this study, data collection is carefully organized through a series of meetings with the adviser to determine the most appropriate techniques. Before data collection begins, specialists will develop and validate a grand tour and stand-in questions. These questions are designed to guide the researcher objectively during interviews and discussions, ensuring the collection of relevant and significant data. The focus is on participants' experiences, with questions constructed to explore and describe their perspectives rather than to explain or test hypotheses. This approach helps maintain a perspective free from preconceptions and biases.

Additionally, approval is sought from the school principal of the institutions where the identified participants are enrolled to conduct the study. In this research, five specific participants were selected based on recommendations from their subject teachers and criteria established through snowball purposive sampling. Following approval, an informed consent form is provided to the participants before data collection begins.

Further, participants were informed of their choice to reject or say "no" to the researcher's invitation. They have made their decision, the date and time of their availability have been determined, and they have been adequately briefed about the interview procedure. They were made aware of the confidentiality of their responses, as well as their option to speak or not express themselves at any moment; I confirmed that they understood the in-depth interview.

Furthermore, the interview was videotaped, audiotaped, documented by a notetaker, and transcribed by the researcher, each participant received a written consent certificate confirming that an in-depth critical informant interview had taken place. In-depth interviews with the five specified participants will be undertaken to obtain qualitative information. Data collection consists of a virtual interview via Google Meet, transcripts, audio recordings, and personal notes elicited by the participants' language and conduct. I conducted early surveys and distributed questionnaires online via Google Forms, as well as gathering and accumulating comprehensive records that led to the study's goal.

Similarly, the interview focused on the experiences of senior high school students at Fatima National High School who are claimed to be hooked to computer games. Following the interview, the researcher verbatim recorded the participants' comments and utilized the coding approach to identify common responses to construct a theme. Each participant's statement was carefully read, line by line. To assess the findings, I sought out recognized patterns or evaluated how the facts were related to the propositions and criteria. When examining the research subject, I construct a list of potential approaches and consult with my adviser about how I can collect the information I need. The thoughts were methodically gathered, sorted, and presented one after the other to highlight the participants' relevant and significant responses. (Aspers & Corte, 2019).

Ethical Considerations

Moreover, there was a primary ethical consideration that had distinct implications for this qualitative research. These issues and concerns might arise mainly from the methodology involved in this study. The ethical challenges in this research concern the problems of the proper operation of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. This study followed the guidelines for ethical considerations set by the RMMC Ethics and Review Committee, especially when it came to the population and data, which included, but were not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The option to participate was given to the participants without any mention of a plan for consequences, compensation, or lost benefits. After explaining the goals and advantages of the study to the participants, their rights to contribute to the body of knowledge were.

Therefore, it is carefully considered and anticipated. Participants in this study were not coerced into taking part. If they become uncomfortable while participating in the study, they can stop.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Participants had the right to privacy, which should not be violated without their informed consent in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards the fundamental human right to privacy. One approach to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study is to provide survey respondents with the choice to withhold their identities from the questionnaire. Besides, confidentiality and privacy were maintained by not publishing the demographic data of the informants, such as their age, gender, occupation, employment, and disease, if any. Hence, their identity was kept confidential for safety purposes.

Informed Consent Process. The goals, methods, and benefits of the research were explained to the people who might take part in the study as thoroughly as possible within the scope of the study. I obtained the participant's consent, indicating their voluntary participation in written form. It tells the participants everything they need to know about the survey and how it was done. The participants were asked to affix their signatures to the informed consent form, confirming that they voluntarily agreed to participate in the survey. Since the people who answered the study were adults who could give their consent, there was no need to ask their parents for permission.

Also, all the information that I gathered was safe and would only be shared with people who gave their informed consent. The participants would feel like they were in charge of their data, which would make them less worried that it would be used in a way they did not want.

Recruitment. The participants were informed of why they had become part of the study. So that the participants could understand the study, I told them why it was being done. This helped the participants figure out what the study was really about. Apart from the letter, I gave the rationale for the research and its significance.

Risks. In this study, it was just as essential to keep the people taking part from getting hurt. The study prioritized the welfare of the participants. Furthermore, the participant's identity was confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. As the researcher, I had to ensure that the people who took the survey were physically, emotionally, and socially ready.

Benefits. Phenomenological inquiry into DOTA players' experiences can provide valuable insights for various stakeholders, including game developers, educators, parents, mental health professionals, and researchers such as;

In-Depth Insight into Player Experiences: This research provides a deep understanding of how DOTA players experience and interpret their interactions within the game. It sheds light on their narratives, motivations, and challenges, offering a comprehensive view of their gaming lives.

Enhanced Awareness of Psychological Impacts: By exploring the lived experiences of players, the study reveals both positive and negative psychological effects of gaming, such as changes in emotional stability, stress levels, and social interactions,

Improved Game Design and Development: Insights from the study can inform game developers about players' needs, preferences, and pain points. This feedback can be used to enhance the game design, making it more engaging and supportive of positive player experiences.

Guidance for Parents and Educators: Understanding players' experiences can help parents and educators recognize the impact of gaming on adolescents. It provides a basis for developing strategies to manage gaming habits, promote balanced use, and address potential issues related to excessive gaming.

Informing Mental Health Interventions: The findings can assist mental health professionals in designing targeted interventions for players experiencing gaming-related matters. It highlights specific areas where players might need support, such as managing stress or improving social interactions.

Contribution to Academic Knowledge: This study adds to the existing body of research on gaming and phenomenology. It provides valuable data for scholars interested in the psychological and social dimensions of gaming, advancing a better comprehension of this intricate phenomenon and

Supporting Positive Gaming Cultures. By highlighting the social and collaborative aspects of gaming, the study can promote a more nuanced view of gaming culture. It underscores the potential for games like DOTA to foster teamwork, communication skills, and community building.

Plagiarism. As a researcher, I need to have positive character and integrity, which are associated with moral virtues and values. To write a credible research paper, I must know more about plagiarism.

Fabrication. The study had no indication or cue of a purposeful misinterpretation. There was no fabrication of data or results, nor was there any deliberate presentation of false conclusions. I used and combined information and other inferential theories.

Falsification. The study did not indicate deliberately falsifying the work to conform to a model or theoretical expectation, nor any indication of overstating or exaggeration. Likewise, this study did not adhere to manipulating the data, which involved formulating statements or disregarding important details, maneuvering materials, tools, or methodologies that would mislead others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The study had no trace of a conflict of interest. More importantly, the disclosure of COI is a set of conditions under which professional judgment concerning primary interests is exercised. Also, I had no power or control over the people who

took part in the study, so they were forced to do so.

Deceit. The study had no trace of misleading the participants about any possible danger. There was much protection for the rights of the people who took part in this study, especially since they had gone to college, so fair and reasonable rules were followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. As a researcher, I have followed protocols throughout the study. The first step was getting permission from the panelists, the adviser, and the RMMCERC committee to collect data. The study began with a formal request for permission addressed to the Command of the Air Education Training and Doctrine Command. Upon approval, the researcher conducted interviews with participants. Before each interview, the researcher visited the participants' offices to inform them of the intent and obtain consent for the interview and recording. Schedules were arranged at the convenience of the participants.

Authorship. I am a current student at the RMMC Graduate School. I made many changes to this thesis manuscript based on what my adviser had suggested. Furthermore, my adviser guided me until the completion of this paper.

Thus, the refinement of the paper was made possible through the guidance of my adviser. I also followed the standards of the RMMC Ethics Review Committee for guidelines on ethical considerations.

Results and Discussion

The findings were classified according to the description of the individual participant and the categorizing of data or the coding method analysis of the answers to the shared experiences of the Defense of the Ancient Players to create a theme.

3.1. Participants

Pudge is a male and a bona fide grade 12 student of Fatima National High School for the school year 2019-2020; his father was a government employee while his mother was a plain housewife; they lived in employee village at Barangay Fatima, General Santos City. He plays 9 to 10 hours a day, and his rank in Defense of the Ancients was Ancient 3.

Invoker is a male and a bona fide grade 12 student of Fatima National High School for the school year 2019-2020; his father was a subcontractor of the Department of Labor and Employment, while his mother was a plain housewife. They lived in Barangay Fatima, Uhaw, General Santos City. He plays 6 to 8 hours a day, and his rank in Defense of the Ancients was Ancient 2.

Lion, aged 19, male and a bonafide grade 12 student of Fatima National High School for the school year 2019-2020; his father was a construction worker while his mother was a plain Housewife. They lived in Block 25, Employees Village of Barangay Fatima, Uhaw, General Santos City. He plays 6 to 8 hours a day, and his rank in Defense of the Ancients was Ancient 4.

Juggernaut, aged 19, male and a bonafide grade 12 student of Fatima National High School for the school year 2019-2020.

While his father was a Carpenter while his mother was a collector at Century Canning Company. They lived in Purok Ondok Gawan, Barangay San Jose, General Santos City. He plays 6 to 8 hours a day, and his rank in Defense of the Ancients was Ancient 1.

Puck, aged 19, male and a bonafide grade 12 student of Fatima National High School for the school year 2019-2020; his father was a Fisherman while his mother was a plain Housewife. They lived in Purok 20, Block 1, Lot 11, Barangay Fatima, Uhaw, General Santos City. He plays 4 to 8 hours a day, and his rank in Defense of the Ancients was Ancient 3.

3.2. Categorization of Data

Moreover, I conducted an in-depth interview among the five specified participants to gather relevant data and describe their experiences as Defense of the Ancients Players. Transcription was made carefully. The data were collected and classified according to its category and relevance. Then, the themes through the research questions are formulated.

Further, the theme analysis, according to Blandford, Ann, is described as a procedure that permits the researcher to get started analyzing the interview data. Still, there is much learning involved in carrying out the analysis. Theme analysis is significant in a qualitative research method because it is widely used across a range of research questions. It is a substantial approach in research where you are trying to find out something about personal views, opinions, knowledge, experiences, and values from qualitative facts by Caulfield, Jack. It is a method wherein the researcher identifies, analyzes, organizes, describes, and reports the themes found in the data.

Furthermore, the analysis of the participants' experiences in the Defense of the Ancients has drawn. Three (3) primary themes describe the experiences of the DOTA Players in the Defense of the Ancients online game and the impact of these experiences on their lives. The participants' responses were categorized into three parts: (Q1) the insights of the DOTA Players description of their Lived experiences in DOTA game; (Q2) their feelings as DOTA players; (Q3) the effects of Defense of the Ancients to their lives.

Therefore, Themes were systematically drawn in tables to secure coherence and conformity. To guarantee the credibility of data gathered, firm record-keeping and securing interpretations of information are coherent and transparent. In the context of this study, I prepared appropriate and valid research instruments, such as in-depth interviews and observations, which are essential to secure the validity of the information gathered. The participants' physical expressions, intonations, and gestures observed by the researcher from the participants throughout the in-depth interview process are included in the field notes.

Views of the Defense of the Ancients Players as to Strengthen Social Connections

We, as human beings, are inherently social animals or creatures. Based on our history, as we go back to our past ways of life and culture, we can trace that humans have traveled, hunted, and thrived in social groups for good reason. Social groups provide us with an essential more than just a component of our personality; they also impart to us a set of abilities that facilitate daily living. In a society where isolation is growing, feeling socially connected is more critical than ever.

Moreover, the benefits of social connectedness should be noticed. Social connections improve the quality of life and shape your everyday life and well-being. It does not always imply being physically present with others in the strict sense, but rather a person's perception of feeling understood and a part of a community. Friendships and Peers offer a number of mental advantages for health, like stronger sensations of belonging and purpose, increased levels of happiness, reduced levels of stress, loneliness, and anxieties, and improved self-worth and confidence. Some conducted studies found that respondents with inadequate and those who felt they had insufficient social support were more likely to experience mental health ailments such as anxiety and depression.

Participants describe their experiences with DOTA playing

Since video games have started to change how people interact, there has been worry about how the behaviors of individual gamers are affected, which has become an increasing issue. Researchers predominantly focused on the behavioral changes within individual gamer participants and have begun to analyze how they have been affected by video games, particularly DOTA.

Clearly, this allows the games to be played remotely. The five primary informants' replies describe their actual Defense of the Ancients gameplay experiences. DOTA is becoming more popular among Filipino teenagers, especially in senior high school, when they are regularly influenced by their friends, friends of their friends, or familiar friends. As the internet's popularity and acceptance grew, the DOTA game evolved into a social tool for those looking to strengthen their social ties. Players can play games together over great distances and converse via an audio interface.

In fact, users can subscribe to an MMORPG (massively multiplayer online role-playing game) and play alongside thousands of other players at any time. Players revealed Views of the Participants as Players on DOTA: These are ascertained from their statements:

Yes maam, Ano maam, DOTA is ano maam, a multiplayer game that players needed to do the farming and get gold to develop and buy equipment (hold his forehead). Each team has ano, 12 torrents to defend and 1 ancient to defend maam., Ahh,, DOTA maam eh ano, it helps me meet a lot of new friends and to avoid my loneliness maam, kasi kapag ano maam, may saloobin ako maam, ano, dinadaan ko nalang sa paglalaro ng DOTA para makalimutan ko mga problema ko maam. Ano maam, noong una maam ano lang, mga kaibigan ko lang ang naglalaro pero nung tingnan ko ano kasi maam,, yung teamfights nila maam at yung graphics kasi ano kapag ikaw naglalaro maam, ang ganda tingnan, kaya ganyan ano na” (P2_Lines 68,70,76)

Yes maam, what DOTA is a multiplayer game that players needed to do the farming and get gold to develop and buy equipments (holding his forehead). Each team has 12 torrents to defend and 1 ancient to defend maam. Ahh,,DOTA maam helps me meet a lot of new friends and to avoid my loneliness maam, because when I have inner thoughts I just let it passed through playing to forget my problem. Before maam my friends only play but when I see their teamfights and the graphics because when you played it maam it so beautiful to see that is why?

The views of participants reflects to their statements:

And P4 Added; “DOTA 2 is a multiplayer online battle arena game which two (2) teams of five(5) players compete to collectively destroy a large structure defended by the opposing team known as Ancients. In my opinion maam, the DOTA game is interesting because there are lots of people who play it and because it is also different from other 5 on 5 games. DOTA game is so cool and lot of people also play it also, that I will be tempted to play because of my friends. (P4_Lines 164,166,172).

Yes maam. DOTA has two (2) teams composing of Dire and Radiant, every team need five (5) persons and need to defend the torrents, at the same time, you need to push the enemies torrents to get the victory.

DOTA helps me to escape from problems, stress, and anxiety. Uhm,, nalilibang kasi ako kapag naglalaro ng DOTA maam, nakakalimutan ko lahat ng problema. Uhm,,It draws my attention especially the good graphics at the same time you can customize the graphics as best as you can (P5_Lines 210,214,218,222).

Yes maam, DOTA has two (2) teams composing of Dire and Radiant, every team need five (5) persons and need to defend the torrents, at the same time, you need to push the enemies torrents to get the victory. DOTA helps me escape my problems, stress, and anxiety. Uhm. I'm having fun when I played DOTA maam, I forget all my problems. It draws my attention especially the good graphics at the same time you can customize the graphics as best as you can.

Team fighting, through this, I can have and meet many friends and also skip my responsibility at home. Kasi, pag naglalaro kasi ako maam nakakalimutan ko yung mga problema ko maam at nagging kampante din ako maam. The first and important aspect of the popularity of DOTA2 is that the game is a teamgame and you can sit with your friends and play together. (P1_Lines 4,6,10,16).

Team fighting, through this, I can have and meet many friends and also skip my responsibility at home, because if I play maam I

forget all my problems and I felt comfortable also maam. The first and important aspect of the popularity of DOTA 2 is that the game is a team game and you can still sit with your friends and play together.

Indeed, Social connections are definitely central to our wellbeing. Human lives are very different and unique. Escaping from the demands and complexities of social interaction is even more necessary. Having friends and family fulfills a fundamental human desire to belong, to be supported, appreciated, and socially connected to others. Connecting socially also provides other health and wellbeing benefits. Some related studies also found that social connections can really help you live longer and impact your mental and physical wellbeing.

Additionally, most people and individuals with stronger social relationships had a higher chance of survival. This was consistent across a variety of characteristics, including age, gender, beginning health status, and cause of death, for it can also decrease your risk of suicide: Several factors increase or decrease people's risk of suicide. One of these characteristics is connectedness; according to its definition, relationships are the degree to which an individual or group shares resources, is connected to others, or is in intimate social circles. It has a vital role in preventing suicidal thoughts and behaviors.

While Connectedness Matters. High-quality relationships because they can help people live longer, healthier lives. Maslow's model is often divided into two categories: esteem needs, which must be satisfied to prevent negative consequences, and growth needs, symbolized by self-actualization, which are linked to personal development and fulfillment; deficiency needs.

On the other hand, include physiological, safety, love, and belonging needs. Understanding how these needs are addressed can provide insights into how supportive relationships counteract the effects of loneliness and social isolation and enhance overall wellbeing. Supportive and inclusive relationships play a crucial role in mitigating the harmful health effects of loneliness and social isolation.

Maslow's hierarchy of needs, a motivational theory in psychology, offers a framework for understanding human needs through a five-tier model often depicted as a pyramid. The hierarchy is structured as follows: Physiological Needs:

Moreover, These are the necessities for survival, such as food, water, and clothing. Safety Needs: This level includes the need for security and stability, such as job security and personal safety. Love and Belonging Needs: This tier involves the need for social relationships, friendship, and a sense of Belonging. Esteem Needs: This level encompasses the need for self-esteem and the esteem of others, including feelings of accomplishment and recognition. Self-Actualization: At the top of the hierarchy, self-actualization refers to the realization of personal potential, self-fulfillment, and seeking personal growth.

As a result, in the context of this study, the five participants were still in the third stage of deficient needs, defined as social needs or belongingness. Deprivation generates deficit needs, which are thought to inspire people when not met; such desires grow stronger the longer they are denied; the longer a person goes without receiving much care and attention from their families and loved ones, the more hungry they become for acceptance and approval from others. Similar to observations made during one-on-one in-depth interviews, many participants reported experiencing a sense of emptiness and social deficit.

Consequently, which they felt was not being adequately addressed by their loved ones and families. For these individuals, playing DOTA became a primary means of addressing their social shortcomings. The game became an integral part of their daily routine, with a significant portion of their time dedicated to playing Defense of the Ancients. Participants viewed DOTA as a pleasurable and entertaining escape from real-world problems, providing them with amusement and recreation. The game offered them a sense of fulfillment and connection that they found lacking in other areas of their lives. In the context of this study, it is evident that playing DOTA provides players with a sense of Belonging, which is a primary factor in their affinity for the game.

As a result, DOTA fosters personal connections and community among players, a feature that became particularly significant during the COVID-19 pandemic. The quarantine period had a profound detrimental effect on mental health, resulting in elevated sentiments of isolation and loneliness. Many individuals have turned to online games as a means of social interaction. In this digital space, players were able to connect with others who shared similar interests, offering a semblance of community and support. For the five specified participants, DOTA played a significant role in mitigating feelings of loneliness and enhancing their mental wellbeing. The game provided a platform for meaningful social interactions, which contributed positively to their mental health during a challenging period. DOTA has become immensely popular in the Philippines, with a significant and growing number of Filipinos participating in the game. The increasing engagement of Filipino youth with DOTA reflects its widespread appeal and highlights its role as an essential social activity in the country.

In addition, as more individuals become involved, the game's influence on social interactions and community building continues to expand. The online social environment created by the game alleviates significant pressure, allowing players to develop and strengthen their social skills in a more comfortable setting.

This virtual interaction provides a valuable space for players to practice communication and build relationships without the immediate pressures of face-to-face encounters.

DOTA as Recreational Activity and Amusement

Apart from this, the advancement of technology has dramatically transformed the way people experience life and spend their leisure

time. In the past, young people often enjoyed outdoor games as their primary form of recreation. Today, however, video gaming has become a predominant pastime for many. Recreation is defined as an activity pursued during discretionary time—time spent away from obligatory tasks such as work or study. It fulfills a fundamental human need to engage in enjoyable, stimulating activities. Recreational activities are typically chosen for their capacity to refresh the body and mind, offering pleasure and fun.

Some common examples of recreational activities include walking, swimming, meditation, reading, dancing, playing games, and browsing the internet. Amusement, on the other hand, encompasses a variety of entertainment options and events that provide enjoyment, such as mechanical rides, water rides, shows, theme exhibits, and picnic grounds. Among contemporary recreational activities, diverse games like DOTA have achieved notable popularity and enduring appeal. With its vast and enthusiastic global audience,

As a result, video gaming has become a central aspect of daily life and cultural practices. The integration of gaming into home and mobile life, facilitated by the increasing capabilities of smartphones, has made video gaming a mainstream leisure activity. Games like DOTA are now deeply embedded in modern recreational practices. This evolution in leisure activities has prompted leisure studies to focus on analyzing and understanding the impact and significance of video gaming in contemporary society.

This notion is expressed by the following statements:

Ahh,,(looking around) DOTA 2 capture my attention through FB (Facebook) videos maam, may nakikita akong magandang laro at malaki din yung price pole at easy to play maam.” (P3_Line 130).

Ahh,,(looking around) DOTA 2 capture my attention through FB (Facebook) videos maam, I see a beautiful game and at the same time it has a big prize pole and easy to play maam..

In my opinion maam, the DOTA game is interesting because there are lots of people who play it and because it is also different from other 5 on 5 games.” (P4_Line 166).

Ang masasabi ko lang maam sa ano tungkol sa DOTA maam ay ano, sayang lang talaga sa oras pero nakaka-enjoy naman talaga siya laruin, yun lang ang masasabi ko maam.” “Sayang sa oras pero nakaka- enjoy laruin Maam.” (P2_Lines 114&116).

U All I say maam about DOTA is surely a waste of time yet enjoyable to play, that’s all I can say maam .Waste of time yet enjoyable to play.

hm,, it was extremely fun, you can encounter new friends that who can help you enhance your skills in playing DOTA.” (P5_Line 224).

Indeed, a game is a universal form of recreation that generally includes any activity engaged in for diversion or amusement and often establishes a situation that involves a contest or rivalry. Video games are the games most commonly played by adolescents, young adults, and even young children, and they include a wide variety of amusements and pastimes primarily played by youths. Each player performs in turn until he misses, resuming after other players miss unless one wins by performing all positions and strategies. Nowadays, playing video games is a typical kind of amusement. Now that DOTA games have spread throughout their daily lives. In fact, some related research focused on the dominance of experimental ‘effects’ that has led to the need for additional research to explain the more common, less contentious existence of games as a significant leisure activity for billions of people who play them frequently for fun and entertainment, while balancing what is occasionally perceived as moral crusades associated with causation studies. Most of the participant in this study referred to DOTA games as their temporary hang-out activity to refrain from any negativities and life burdens, and they find it interesting to play, for it does bring happiness, joy, fun, excitement, and pleasure in the virtual world they imagined

DOTA as Recreational Therapy and Coping Mechanism

As a result, Play is a powerful tool, particularly for individuals facing physical, emotional, or mental health challenges. Recreational therapy, Which uses structured play and leisure activities can be highly effective in addressing issues.

While these issues. It helps rebuild skills, enhance mood, improve overall quality of life, and strengthen social connections, these benefits highlight the significance of tailored leisure therapy in promoting health and well-being, engaging in recreational activities fosters optimism, resilience, and a positive outlook on life. This attitude not only helps individuals manage daily tasks and responsibilities but also builds tolerance and coping mechanisms to navigate adversity. Having an optimistic outlook and perspective assists DOTA players in dealing with the stresses and negativities created by pressing events, particularly during these difficult times. This notion is expressed in the following statements of the participants:

Ang masasabi ko lang maam sa ano tungkol sa DOTA maam ay ano, sayang lang talaga sa oras pero nakaka-enjoy naman talaga siya laruin, yun lang ang masasabi ko maam. Sayang sa oras pero nakaka- enjoy laruin Maam.” (Transcribed no.2, page180, lines 114&116).

All I can say maam about DOTA is that it was surely a waste of time yet really enjoyable to play maam. (Transcribed no.2, page180,

lines 114&116).

Ahh,,DOTA maam eh ano, it helps me meet a lot of new friends and to avoid my loneliness maam. May saloobin ako maam ano, dinadaan ko nalang sa paglalaro ng DOTA para makalimutan ko mga problema ko maam. Ano maam, the advantages of this game to maam, ano maam, it help me to escape or avoid my loneliness, sadness and anxiety maam, it makes me happy to ano maam to,, bsta kapag naglalaro ako maam. (smiling) (Transcribed no.2, page 169, lines 70&72).

Ahh, DOTA maam helps me meet a lot of new friends and to avoid my loneliness maam. I just let my innerthoughts passed through playing DOTA to forget all my problems. The advantages of this of this game maam is that it help me escape or avoid my my loneliness, sadness and anxiety maam, it makes me happy to whenever I play.

Ahh,,(scratch his forehead, and look around then look up) DOTA can reduce stress, loneliness and you can make friends through online maam. To me, the advantages of this game,,it can make me happy and forget my problems maam. (P3_Lines 122&124).

It becomes my outlet to forget my problem maam.” (P1_line 8).

DOTA helps me to escape from problems, stress and anxiety.The advantages of this game, I can avoid anxiety and loneliness. Uhm,,Nalilibang kasi ako kapag naglalaro ng DOTA maam, nakaklimutan ko lahat ng problema. (P5_lines 214,216 & 218).

DOTA helps me to escape from problems, stress and anxiety. The advantages of this game is I can avoid anxiety and loneliness. Uhm,,because I have fun when I played DOTA maam, I forget all my problems.

Undoubtedly, Recreational therapy benefits people of all ages. It’s often used to help people who are recovering from a stroke, rehabilitating from an injury, illness, or surgery, working to improve motor skills, learning to carry out the activities of daily living independently, being treated for cancer, recovering from a substance use disorder, experiencing anxiety or worries, and feeling isolated or depressed, developing the ability to express their thoughts and emotions (White, 2020).

Moreover, Recreational therapy has a wide range of positive impacts on both physical and mental health, particularly when tailored to individual interests and needs. Participants in this study reported that engaging in games like DOTA helps them cope with difficult situations by providing a temporary escape from their problems. This form of therapy can reduce worries, alleviate negative emotions such as sadness, loneliness, stress, and anxiety, and offer a reprieve from everyday challenges. The benefits of targeted recreational therapy include skill rebuilding, mindset improvement, quality of life enhancement, and strengthened social connections.

Further, Social engagement and brain-stimulating activities, such as memory challenges and video games, play a significant role in these positive outcomes. It’s important to remember that recreational therapy, along with maintaining social relationships and engaging in activities that challenge the mind, contributes to the healthy functioning of the brain (White, 2020).

Aptitude Enrichment

Hence, an Aptitude is a component of a competence to do a certain kind of work at a certain level. Outstanding aptitude can be considered "talent."

Thus, An aptitude may be physical or mental. Aptitude is considered an inborn potential to do certain kinds of work, whether developed or undeveloped, it is a special ability for doing something, it implies a natural liking for some activity and the likelihood of success in it, and it reflects specialized abilities and personal strengths & and weaknesses. One of the advantages is it improves their interpersonal skills, especially on leadership skills.

Besides, One of the biggest debates among educators of today is about whether or not video games are a valid educational tool, back then, teachers were using games to reinforce learning games that dealt with areas of education have been used like some of educational games that makes the virtual learning more interactive. As video games become an everywhere part of today's culture, As an educator and parents we need to turn our attention to how video games are being understood and used in informal and formal settings.

Appropriately and as timely as it can be. Learners’ show that their learning preferences have been strongly shaped by new media technologies like video games, virtual reality environments, the Internet, and social networks. Aside from that, according to the participants of this study, DOTA game is one of the media that can be used for improving and developing interpersonal skills, team communication, eye coordination, concentration, mental alertness, creativity mindset, strategies, critical thinking and multi-tasking ability, when they are playing game online , they use all of their senses to gather information they need that are helpful and important for themselves and for their teams as well, so accordingly, it implies that DOTA playing is the most important process in enhancing people to learn in many things and ways.

Hence, through playing game, they’ve learn something and gained the knowledge and skills through real time experience. These notions is supported by their statements:

Yes maam, the positive effects of this game, I’m having a new friends who can teach me how to enhance my strategy and multi-tasking ability. (P5_Line 234).

I improve my interpersonal skills and “parang nafeel ko maam murag mi upgrade yung paglalaro ko maam, ganun”. . (P1_ Line 34).

I improve my interpersonal skills and I feel maam, like it upgraded my playing, that’s’ it.

However, In line with this matter, the fact that Dota 2 is a strategic game, it strongly implies that rather often the game requires some teamwork. Since it was a multiplayer game it is understood that you have many allies and at the same time opponents, you learn how to make allies works as well. It’s not enough, to have people on your side. You also have to think through how each one is going to contribute in order for you to achieve the goal you have in common. this stimulates them to learn how to delegate and communicate responsibilities.

Apparently, not only that they can this have a positive impact on their day-to-day life, but it can also probably boost their sense of self-worth. These notions is supported by their statements;

Yes maam. Your brain will work. work and you will have a strategy for things and also your critical thinking. (connection error), Yes maam, it improves your critical thinking. (P4_ Lines 184&186).

It improves my eye coordination and team communication and ano maam and ano maam concentration. Kasi maam, mas maano kana sa paligid mo maam mas nasanay kana ba yung mas mabilis kanang makaano (looking his right side wanting to say alert-mind). (P2_ Lines 92&94).

It improves my eye coordination and team communication and concentration maam. Because maam you became more used to the environment and be more alert and fast.

Uhm,, magkakaroon ka ng creativity mindset maam.” (P3&5_ Lines 148&236).

Moreover, as we all know, Learners have diverse knowledge and intelligence, and the strategies in teaching should cater to their differing ways of learning.

Further, this includes innovations such as incorporating electronic games like DOTA for educational purposes. For playing DOTA requires strategy and critical thinking. It is considered higher order thinking skills (HOTS), that is, higher than mere rote memorization was applied. Higher-order thinking skills include critical thinking, analyzing, reasoning, synthesizing, evaluating, and creating, and there are some related studies that assume that; DOTA could develop learners’ order thinking skills. Well, I agree that, in some ways, it could develop learners’ higher order thinking if and was played in moderation. Most of the participants mentioned that once they started, they could no longer stop themselves from playing because they always want to have a rematch, especially if they want to fight for revenge and if their teams lost the game.

Table 1. *Thematic Analysis on the description of thoughts and views of the Lived Experiences among Defense of the Ancients Players/Informants*

<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Multiplayer Game	
Team game	
Collaborate with teams/Develop teamwork	Strengthen Social Connections
Team fights/Team combat	
Encounter new friends/ Meet many friends	
Comfortable	
Enjoyable	
Easy to play	
Huge prices at stake	
Interesting	Recreational Therapy/Coping Mechanism
Extremely Fun	
To forget/Escape Problems	
It avoids Sadness, Loneliness and anxiety	
It reduces stress	
It improves interpersonal skills, eye coordination, concentration and critical thinking	
It develops team communication, mental alertness, a good mindset, strategies and creativity mindset	Aptitude Enrichment
It enhances multi-tasking ability	
Brain will work/function	

Feeling of Players Lived Experienced in Defense of the Ancients as to Adrenalin Rush

Certainly, Adrenaline, also known as epinephrine, is a stress hormone. An adrenaline rush can feel like anxiousness, nervousness, or pure excitement as your body and mind are preparing for an event.

Besides, when your body experiences a great amount of stress from your environment, there is a release of adrenaline, it helps you

focus so you can take on the situation. There are certain activities like sports and games particularly with videogames that give you an adrenaline rush. Competitions in athletic sports and other video games can also give you this rush of epinephrine. This feeling either excites you or amps up your anxiety for whatever event you're facing. In a stressful situation, you may start to feel different like your palms may start to sweat.

Hence, you could be looking for a way out of the situation. Your heart is most likely racing. This is also known as a fight-or-flight experience. Adrenaline causes these symptoms, this stress hormone is created in the adrenal medulla, which is found in your adrenal glands. As your body responds to stress, adrenaline is made and released quickly. This gives you an adrenaline rush. When you're experiencing an adrenaline rush, your muscles are using the glycogen stored in your body. This process helps them maintain strong, extended contractions.

Seemingly, an adrenaline rush is meant to keep you focused and ready to go. One misconception is that you don't feel pain during an adrenaline rush. You just may be too distracted by the adrenaline to experience the full extent of pain. The release of adrenaline helps increase your mental concentration. It doesn't take the pain away, rather it distracts you from the sensation of it.

While, an Adrenaline Rush can heighten your abilities, making you feel invincible. This is ascertained from these statements:

maam.(smiling). I feel I'm on cloud nine (9), because of my extreme happiness maam, kasi masarap kasi sa pakiramdam kapag nanalo ka palagi maam. (P1_Line 26).

Im going to speak English maam (smiling). I feel I'm on,cloud,nine(9),because of my extreme happiness maam, because its so good feel when I always win maam.

"Ano maam, I feel the ano maam,, the excitement in me and the adrenaline rush to my ano,, when you are ano in the middle of the fight, you'll really feel the joy and happiness because of the fighting maam." (P2_Line 80).

"Ahh,,it makes me hyper maam and excited when we are about to clash or teamfight." (P3_Line 134).

"Excited maam, excited when you're in the game and nervous you might lose." (P4_Line 174).

Apparently, the participants of this study believed that by this process it helped them overcome the situation that is causing their negative feelings though, Adrenaline rushes are hard to measure, the exact negative impacts are not fully understood. However, continuous stress and epinephrine released into our body can have negative impacts and these impacts can include high blood pressure and anxiety most prevalent negative impact of the adrenaline rush is the feeling of dizziness, light-headedness, and vision change. Likewise, As they mentioned their experienced on adrenaline rush, they said they start to feel depressed, irritable or unable to stay still. Obviously, which are common things observed on them.

Whereas, inability to sleep and nervousness which are also a common effects of too much adrenaline that most of them mentioned during our one on one in depth interview, if they have a pre-existing condition like cardiovascular disease, it is unhealthy for them to experienced this so called Adrenalin rush. And during their video gaming for it can cause many health problems that is too risky or damaging to their heart. Overexposure to adrenaline can cause:

Further, Digestive problem, Cardiovascular disease, Weight gain, Metabolic issues, Headaches, High blood pressure, Memory and concentration impairment, Sleep disorders, Anxiety, and Depression. This phenomenological study on DOTA players present lived experiences revealed their adversities and difficulties in adopting this new normal was ascertained from their present situations and that they are confronted with challenges in terms of their mental and emotional state and conditions.

Positive and Pleasant Feelings

Moreover, Playing Dota2 involves completing goals, reaching objectives, and accomplishing numerous tasks. The satisfaction that every gamer feels whenever they cross off a task from a list or receive a badge or a trophy for completing a mission positively affects their self-esteem mental state, and even their feelings. This is also one of the reasons why learners of Fatima National High School look for video shops so often nowadays because there they can find their happiness, joy and satisfaction. Aside from that, a big advantage of online games is also the fact that pro players get huge money that actually brings income on the part of the player or gamer, and they consider making money is a serious task to complete.

Hence, they used their knowledge and skills for a way to switch to the productive side. Not only completing tasks makes them feel good about themselves. it also makes it easier to complete other more difficult tasks they have on their purpose, it develops their sense of accomplishment. Most of the participants in this study refer video games as their temporary hang out activity to refrain from any negativities and life burdens.

Moreover, DOTA also brought to them a temporary relief from their baggages and other misfortunes that caused them lots of trouble in mind and emotionally created stressed and anxieties in their daily lives. The following statements reflect this matter:

I feel so happy and excited maam, that's the only thing I felt during I play DOTA.

I feel ano maam, siyempre masaya maam, kasi panalo ka na namn, tapos mamotivate mo naman sarili mo na maglaro na naman at magsayang na nama ng pera. (Laughing). (P2_ Line 86).

Of course I feel what maam because you win again then, repeatedly, you motivate yourself to play and your money will be wasted again. (laughing).

It makes me feel proud and satisfied maam especially when I will win strikes repeatedly.

I feel so proud and good especially if our team is leading to a victory. (P5_Line 228).

I'm proud because I did everything just to win the game and happy. (P4_Line 178).

Clearly, Participants experience diverse problems in dealing with their lives and those experiences in the new normal has impacted their views and feelings on how they perform their responsibilities as complexities and adjustments arise. In which is needed to be address and resolve in order for them to function normally, effectively and efficiently, they indulge themselves to DOTA gaming where they could find happiness, enjoyment and fun and feel more relax and excited

As a result, their adjustments to the present new normal setting become easy for them which are apparent into their shared experiences and feelings.

Negative and Unpleasant Feelings

While, failure doesn't feel good especially in a game, not in real life. Losing a game over and over is frustrating, but it also helps you learn how to cope with this frustration. It's actually one of the reasons why it's advised that children should engaged more in sports and also sometimes play video games like DOTA for It can help them practice more on dealing with these emotions and communicating them in a healthy way. However, instead of teaching them to learn how to get over their failures and try again, for the player they cannot deny the fact, that they still felt some negativities and unpleasant feelings especially if they don't achieve what they longed for or their target of winning the game.

This assumption is reflected in these following statements:

Just Wait maam, I feel disheartened and depressed if our team lose the game." "Yes maam, sad, because I don't have money for playing DOTA. I'm disappointed to myself and I'm so jealous to other gamer because they can afford to play." (P1_Lines 28 &30).

I feel like sad, dissatisfied but I keep saying to myself that being defeated is always part of the game." "Yes, and not really good. I feel so weak, I can't feel the presence of my favourite hero then suddenly I feel like disappointed because I don't have money to spend playing DOTA." (P5_Lines 230&232).

Wait maam, I feel disheartened and depressed if our team lose the game. Yes maam, sad, because I don't have money for playing DOTA. I'm disappointed to myself and I'm so jealous to other gamer because they can afford to play. (P1_Lines 28 &30).

This assumption is reflected in these following statements:

Siyempre maam, malungkot kasi yung ano yung pera mo pinaglalaro mo lang para dapat Manalo pero natalo kaya sayang yung pera pero deretso parin gusto mo parin maglaro kasi gusto mo talagang Manalo. Yes maam, there is always a day that I can't play DOTA and it makes me feel bad, ano,,frustrated and sad at the same time, because I really wanted to play DOTA maam, but, I still can't because I don't have a lot of money to pay for the internet maam. (P2_Lines 88&90).

Of course maam, lonely because the money I spent is intended only for the win but it loses so it's a waste of money yet still willing to play in order to win. Yes maam, there's always a day that I can't play DOTA and it makes me feel bad, frustrated and sad at the same time, because I really wanted to play DOTA maam, but I can't because I don't have a lot of money to pay for the internet maam.

I feel tired and unsatisfied because, natatapos akong maglaro maam madaling araw na maam. I feel tired and unsatisfied maam. Uhm,, due to lack of sleep maam. I cannot play sometimes and due to lack of money maam, I feel so bad, sad and annoyed maam

I feel tired and dissatisfied because, I finished my game at dawn already maam. I feel tired and unsatisfied maam. Uhm,, due to lack of sleep maam. I cannot play sometimes and due to lack of money maam. I feel so bad, sad and annoyed maam.

Disgusting to play the next game because you might lose again. (both smiling). I can miss playing DOTA and its also boring because I can't play. (P4_Lines 180&182).

I feel like sad, dissatisfied but I keep saying to myself that being defeated is always part of the game. Yes, and not really good. I feel so weak. I can't feel the presence of my favorite hero then suddenly I feel like disappointed because I don't have money to spend playing DOTA. (P5_Lines 230&232).

According to the participants of this study, Dota is a truly one of the most entertaining online game today because of its awesome

graphics, and which is really an engaging game to play. This is one main factor why learners choose to play this game particularly to spend their time aside from its popularity. The entire idea of playing one of the most popular games not just in the country but in the world will make them more curious and interested.

After all, Social media and word of mouth has a serious grab onto people. Seeing how young people, including learners, which is the most are its target audience of this game, meanwhile, the popularity of this game is definitely the number one reason why more and more of them start playing over and over again. Despite of having experienced negative and unpleasant feelings like depression, frustration and loneliness and others which they get and might feel throughout playing DOTA.

Table 2. *Thematic Analysis on the Lived Experiences of Defense of the Ancients Players; According to their feelings.*

<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Extreme Happiness	
Felt on Cloud 9	
Adrenalin Rush	Adrenalin Rush
Excited/ Excitement	
Hyper/Active	
Felt Nervous	
Happy/ Happiness	
Joy	
Felt Motivated	Positive and Pleasant Feelings
Satisfied/Satisfaction	
Proud, Good	
Disheartened	
Jealous	
Feeling Bad, Sad	
Depressed	
Frustrated	
Lonely	
Tired/Tiresome	Negative and Umpleasant feelings
Hungry	
Unsatisfied/Dissatisfied	
Annoyed	
Disgusted	
Bored/Boredom	
Dissappointed	
So weak	

Effects of DOTA in the Lived Experiences of Player as to Develop Inferiority Complex and Low Self-Esteem

Indeed, A psychological condition that exists when a person's feelings of inadequacy are so intense that daily living is impaired. According to Adler, all humans experience feelings of inferiority as children and spend the rest of their lives trying to compensate for those feelings.

As people replace the dependence of childhood with the independence of adulthood, the feelings of inferiority persist in varying intensity in different people.

For some people, the sense of inferiority serves as a positive motivating factor, as they strive to improve themselves in an effort to neutralize the negative feelings of inferiority. Some, however, become dominated and, as a result, crippled by an overwhelming sense of inadequacy. These people, whose thoughts are so overtaken by these feelings that they cannot function normally, are said to have an inferiority complex. According to a study published in September 2014 in the North American Journal of Medical Sciences.

Furthermore, Most Common Symptoms; Symptoms of inferiority complex are more than just periodic bouts of poor self-esteem or concerns about your talents; they are ongoing. Some common symptoms include: Feeling insecure, incomplete, or unworthy, Withdrawal from everyday activities and social situations, Comparing yourself to others, Feelings of hostility, frustration, nervousness, or aggression, Insomnia, Inability to complete tasks, Signs of depression, anxiety, or other mental health disorders. Probably, someone with inferiority complex frequently blames others for their problems and attributes their weaknesses to factors they can't control, such as ho According to the Depression Alliance.

While, such acts are frequently used to compensate for unfavorable self-perceptions. Low self-esteem is defined as a lack of confidence in one's own identity and abilities. They frequently feel incompetent, neglected, or inadequate. In reality, people with low self-esteem are constantly fearful of making mistakes or disappointing others. Depression/sadness, anxieties, low mood, avoiding social situations, feelings of inadequacy, comparing oneself negatively to others.

Particularly difficulty accepting compliments, neglect of one's own needs emotional ones, putting others' needs ahead of one's own,

low expectations, and difficulty forming/maintaining relationships are some of the most common characteristics of low self-esteem. As a result, this study determined how Dota 2 affects the participants' physical and mental health, academic performance, and future ambitions, as well as their relationships with family and loved ones. Despite the fact that it is detrimental for them, they cannot afford to stop and have not considered abandoning Dota totally. This assumption is expressed from these statements:

It makes me more aggressive gamer to the extent that I steal my neighbor's domestic chicken maam, Kasi maam nung,, nung Grade nine (9) ata ako maam, (clearing his throat), "Kumukuha talaga ako ng manok sa kapitbahay naming, kasi para mayroon lang akong panlaro sa computer, mahirap lang kasi ako noon maam kasi, wala ring trabaho yung mama ko at sa kapatid lang ako umaasa maam eh." "Uhhh,,,it affects my credibilityfor they reported me to our barangay, kasi maam nung nagnakaw kami ng manok maam nahuli din kami ng kapitbahay naming noon at yun nabarangay kami maam." (P1_ Lines 38&40).

It makes me more aggressive gamer to the extent that I steal my neighbor's domestic chicken maam, because maam when I was like in Grade nine (9), (clearing throat), I used to steal chicken from our neighbor just to have some money for DOTA game, because before my mother have no work, and I only depend on my sibling. Uhhh,,, it affects my credibility for there was a time they reported me to our barangay, because they caught us stealing their chicken that's why we go to the barangay maam.

Ano maam, it destroy my social life and ruined my academic performance and I lost my confidence to talk with other people because mas gusto ko nalang maglaro ng DOTA, kasi yung shyness ko sa ano maam, mas nasasayahan ako maam sa computeran maam." P2_Line 102).

Maam, it destroy my social life and ruined my academic performance and I lost my confidence to talk with other people because I prefer to play Dota because of my shyness maam, I am more happy at computer shop maam.

Yes, I learn to argue with my parents,, I am satisfied to be alone rather than to be with someone." (P4&5_Lines 200&220).

Besides, People with an inferiority complex frequently exhibit characteristics of arrogance or narcissism, however this is not always true. Instead, it's a coping mechanism for a pervasive sense of insecurity. These symptoms may include: being highly competitive, being a perfectionist or sensitive to criticism, finding faults in others, seeking attention, and having difficulty admitting mistakes. Individuals with inferiority complexes have often undergone childhood traumas that contribute to their symptoms; one solitary episode is rarely enough to precipitate a long-term disease. Inferiority Complex: The inclination to blame others.

Subsequently, a person with an inferiority complex typically blames others for their difficulties and assigns their inadequacies to factors beyond their control, such as how they were reared. According to the Depression Alliance, such acts are frequently performed to compensate for negative self-esteem.

Health Risks or Physical, Mental, and Psychological Health Deficiency

Most of e-sports players pay a physical price like difficulty in sleeping which results to Insomnia together with deteriorating eyesight because of lack of sleep, digestive problems because of no time to eat,and being tiresome.

In addition, because of lack of body or physical exercise, Headaches, stomach ache and wrist and hand damage because of lack of self-control etc.. Though it's impossible, how can they get injuries when they play games?" These effects can vary from one learner to another but, the more addicted they become, the worse will this all become. Dota will affect the Bothe Physical and mental health like their sleeping hours and the studies. Instead of studying, the learners prefer to sit on a computer, spending all his time playing Dota regardless of these consequences.

Actually, they mentioned that It only starts as a mode of entertainment and a short break from studies turns into a full-time job with more disadvantages than benefits. That's when Dota or any other video game becomes dangerous for the one who plays it. This assumption is expressed from these statements:

I develop insomnia, it caused me headache and unstable ability to focus." "I can't eat on time, because I've been focusing to playing DOTA and it makes me forgetful maam. (P1_Lines 48&36).

Yes maam, kasi maam ano, medyo nahihirapan akong matulog ng maaga ngayon maam, tapos, madali na akong mapikon, tapos, nakakasira siya sa ano maam, ano, nakakalimutan ko na yung mga bagay bagay na mas madali na ako nakakalimot ngayon sa pagpupuyat man god maam." "Paspas nako kapuyon, ana god maam, kulang na sa exercise ako lawas, dili nako active (looking up and around because of some noise occurred). (Both smiling). (P2_ Lines 106&108).

Uhm,,, I'm becoming tiresome, at saka nagkaron ng sakit ng ulo, sakit ng tiyan and I develop insomnia maam, nahihirapan ng matulog sa gabi maam." (P3_Line 156).

Yes maam because, quiet a bit, I can hardly sleep early now maam. And I easily get annoyed and currently, became forgetful due to lack of sleep maam, I get easily tired maam, my body is lack of exercise and not active.(looking up and around because of some noise interruptions).

Nakakapekto sa kanilang pakikinig sa klase, maging lutang ang kanilang pag-iisip at nakafocus lang sila sa game, wala silang

gusto gawin kundi laro laro lang maam.” (P5_Lines 244,238&250).

It affects their class listening, their minds floats and only focused on the the game and they don't want to do anything except playing and playing only maam.

Yes maam, You don't have a (pauses), You don't have a good diet and you can't sleep early because of playing and it's easy to be weak. “ The bad thing about playing is that they can no longer control and a lot of pain it gets, headache due to overdo and lack of money due to addiction of playing DOTA.” “After I play,

Moreover, the majority of the participants noted frequent health problems they experienced while addicted to DOTA gaming, such as insomnia or difficulties sleeping owing to a lack of sleep and overdoing it in the game. During their interview, they stated that they became physically inactive and tired as a result of a lack of sleep, lack of physical activity, and a lack of self-control when playing. They also highlighted digestive issues.

Such as stomach aches and a loss of their healthy appetite. Eating is irrelevant to them since they get the same satisfaction from both playing and eating. As a result, the body's immune systems are getting weaker and may now exposed to the different viruses and common diseases., and they also stated that because they always forget to eat.that lead them to become more irritable, aggressive, stress and anxiety which may lead to more serious mental health problems if not controlled and remedied.

Effects on their Academic Performance

According to the participants of this study, when they mention the effects of Dota on their academic performance, they don't just mean this as it built negative connotation in fact they characterize it as fun and enjoyable game and most of them stated that they used this for recreation and to take a break only But, DOTA games now affects their lives in so many ways.

Besides, DOTA, as one of the most played and famous online game with the touch of modern technology, it become more than just play. It become an addiction., when it became an addiction, it became difficult and hard for the parents and to the gamers to end what has been started. This notion is expressed from these statements:

Yes maam. I don't prioritize my study and I don't have any future plans.” (P1_Line 44).

Ano maam, kapag nahooked kana ng DOTA maam ano, Bale, mawawala na yung ano maam, masisira na yung future ganon yun maam, gaya yan yung ano, Academic performance mo.” “Ay naka depende man na siya maam, pero based sa experience ko maam, nakasira talaga, kasi nagfocus na ako sa laro eh, di ko na iniintindi yung future ko, yung academic studies ko mga ganun maam.” (P2_Lines 98&100).

What maam, if you are hooked to DOTA maam, like disappearance and your future will be destroy something like that maam, for instance, your Academic Performance, it depends however, based on m experience it really destroys me because I only focus on the game, I no longer care for my future like in my academic studies that's it maam.

“The negative effect, I'm becoming forgetful maam and can't get good grades at school” “Yes, because I can't make assignment maam and late at school and I no longer focused on my future plans.” (P3_Lines 152&154).

Moreover, Part of the learners' responsibility is to prioritize their schooling yet, according to the participants of this study, because of DOTA online game they can hardly stop and control themselves in playing once they started. The impact of excessive DOTA gaming on academic performance became evident, as many participants reported difficulties in focusing on their studies. Statements from participants indicated that their time was predominantly consumed by gaming, leading to issues such as low and failing grades. This decline in academic performance was attributed to tardiness, absenteeism, and the inability to complete class activities and other school tasks.

Further, Disordered behavior is often characterized by a disruption in the normal functioning of the behavior in question—here, gaming—which results in psychological and functional consequences. It is important to differentiate between "Gaming Disorder," a specific diagnosis recognized in clinical settings.

While, "gaming disorder" as a broader term that refers to problematic gaming behavior that may not meet the criteria for a formal diagnosis but still impacts an individual's daily functioning and well-being, while, distinguishing between the problem and the individual experiencing it can be challenging. Those affected by Gaming Disorder (GD) seek accurate identification, appropriate treatment, and psychological or pharmacological support to overcome their issues. Specialized treatment centers around the world now address Gaming Disorder, indicating that for individuals who face severe problems due to excessive gaming, professional intervention is often necessary. This specialized care is crucial for managing and mitigating the adverse effects associated with Gaming Disorder.

Effects on their Future Plans

Hence, Aarseth et al. acknowledge that some gamers suffer substantial consequences as a result of playing video games. In fact, some of these co-authors. Participants in this study, are spending too much time on online games daily, and they tend to suffer from worsened learning ability, concentration problems, poor academic performance, and decreased interactions with other people. Despite of the

negative behavior on playing the game, they used to play with it religiously many times a day despite of the many negative and bad effects that DOTA created and brought to their lives and future.

This assumption is expressed from these statements:

Yes maam, I don't prioritize my study and I don't have future plans. Uhm,,,seem like I was focus on playing DOTA maam and seemed like I already lost my future plans in my life maam, that's it. (P2_Line 104).

Yes maam, dati maam ano, gusto ko talaga mag ano maam, pumasok sa mga top universities at maging ano maam, future engineer someday, pero ano maam kasi eto sa pagdodota, nakakalimutan na iyong mga pangarap at iyon wala na, finish na! (P2_Line 104).

Yes maam, before maam I really want to go to some top universities and become a future engineer someday, but because of playing DOTA, I forget my ambition and that's it, It's done!

Yes, because I can't make assignment maam and late at school and I no longer focused on my future plans. (P3_Line 154).

Yes maam, because you are not focused on your plans in life, you are losing your thoughts about the future, because of you're playing DOTA.. (P4_Line 196).

Yes, because I can't even make myself focused in school and still having a low grades and I forget my class activities and I always forget my daily plans. (P5_Line 242).

Unfortunately, no online video game publishers provide referral services nor customer care with regards to video game addiction and these may trigger violence and disruption in the academic performance of the gamers. Disruption in the academic performance of students can cause chaos towards their future.

Effects on their Relationship with Family or Love ones

Furthermore, Playing DOTA, may lead to ruin and destroy the participants' life especially towards handling the relationships with their family and love one's aside from their studies, most of the participants believed that playing video games is good because it can make them happy and escape their problems. and most of the gamer think that it can solve their personal issues in their family or love ones not knowing the fact that actually it can add to their are addiction to DOTA games that cannot easily stop and control themselves from playing.

Which presently, caused them a lot of troubles and problems with regards to dealing in relationship with their friends, loveones and families. This assumption is reflected from these statements:

Yes maam, Ano maam, kasi simula ng naglalaro ako ng DOTA maam, parang I lost my respect to my parents maam, kasi mas madali na akong mapikon ngayon, ano maam, tapos, nagagalit na sila sa akin kasi nasisira ko yung expectation nila sa akin na mas nagfofocus ako sa paglalaro hindi sa studies ko maam." (P2_Line 74).

Yes maam, because since I played DOTA maa,, seem like I lost my respect to my parents maam because I get easily annoyed now maam, then, they got angry with me because I failed their expectation that I focused to much on gaming rather than my studies maam.

My mother is always upset to me because I always forget my house responsibility and my realization is "If I could turn back time I should not be hooked in DOTA game, because it can ruin my relationships to my family maam".. (P3_Line 158).

Uhm, I realized that I've missed a lot of opportunities in life, and also, I have many shortcomings to my parents." (P5_Line 246).

Yes maam, I learn to argue with my parents, I am satisfied to be alone rather than to be with someone." "Kuan maam, sana di ko nalang pinasok ang paglalaro ng DOTA kasi nakakasira sa pamilya maam at relasyon." (P4_Lines 200&202).

Yes maam. I learn to argue with my parents, I am satisfied to be alone rather than to be with someone. The thing maam is that I wish I didn't enter playing DOTA because it destroy family maam and relationship as well.

In this case, most of the players have almost the same experiences being encountered with their families and love ones like they no longer have quality time for their family and loveones and they don't know longer have time to look and find for someone which means they became loner and anti social.

Aside from that they realized that they have missed lots of opportunities and chances in life because of too much focused on the game. it also affects their attitudes and behaviors towards their families and love ones, P1 and P4 mentioned that they learn to argue and fight their parents while P2 said he became irritable and lost his respect to his parents, he fails to match his parents' expectations, leaving them sad and disappointed with him, whereas P3 indicated that he fails to accomplish his domestic chores and obligations, leaving his mother always displeased with him.

Obviously, when we think about someone playing a DOTA game, we rarely consider it dangerous or detrimental. Its main objective is to provide entertainment. After all, the idea of a person being addicted to DOTA is insignificant in compared to other dangerous

substances like alcohol and drugs. However, experts have known about and shown the dangers of DOTA addiction for quite some time.

Table 3. *Thematic Analysis on Lived Experiences of Defense of the Ancients Players; According to the Effects of Defense of the Ancients online gaming to the lives of the Participants.*

<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>	
Became aggressiveness, a thief, anti social, loner	Develop Inferiority complex/low self esteem	
Destroyed Credibility		
Develop shyness	Health Risks/Physical and Mental Health Deficiency	
Develop insomnia		
No time to eat		
Unstable ability to focus		
Absent minded/Forgetful		
Having stress		
Suffered anxiety		
Do not prioritize studies		
No time to study/too much focused in playing		
Unfocused to studies		
Fail to do school responsibilities	Effects on Academic Performance	
Get low/failing grades		
Always get late for school		
Forget dreams and goals in life	Effects of future plans	
No more future plans		
No longer focused on future plans		
Losing thoughts about future		
Forget daily plans		
No more future plans		
Learn to fight with parents/family		
Fail to do House chores/Forget House responsibilities and to achieve parents expectations		
No time for family and to look for someone		Effects on the Relationship with family and loved ones
Lost respect to parents		
Making parents upset		
Destroy/Ruin relationship with family		
Learn to argue and fight with parents		

Discussion

From the data collected on the defense of the ancient players, this response was based on the themes that emerged as presented in the tables. These themes helped the researcher to determine which core ideas to report.

Table 1 revealed that based on my participants' responses if they experienced challenging situations, it can be easier for them to "substitute" those situations with a virtual picture that is convenient and offers the prospect of being able to solve any of their problematic situations.

According to Maslow's theory, we have these basic needs: deficiency or basic needs and developmental or growth needs. According to his hierarchy of needs, it is usually essential for us to first satisfy our deficiency needs. One of them is the social needs or belonging needs before progressing on to meet higher level growth needs, which is true in real-life situations based on the statements of most of the participants. They strengthened their social connections through playing, and they learned to collaborate with teams.

Evidently, the DOTA online game, according to P1, P3, and P4, has common responses; they confirmed that engaging in DOTA, aside from its good features, helps them meet a lot of new friends, which all of them confirmed that it reduces and removed their loneliness/sadness, stress, and anxieties that genuinely made them feel comfortable and P5 described it as an Extremely fun. At the same time, P2 said that it is more enjoyable to play. Thus, it strengthened their Social Connections and improved their quality of life, and it shaped their everyday life and well-being.

However, It does not necessarily mean physically being present with people in a literal sense, someone's subjective experience of feeling understood and connected to others. Some conducted studies found that respondents with inadequate and those who felt they had insufficient social support were more likely to experience mental health conditions like depression and anxiety. Most likely, almost all five Participants described their experiences with DOTA playing; they tended to interact with other individual gamers, learned to multitask multitasking, and collaborated with teams (Smith, 2018).

As a result, based on their responses, particularly in their senior high school years, when they are typically influenced by their friends, friends of their friends, or familiar friends, the internet has become more widely used, and the DOTA game has increasingly become a social tool to strengthen their social connections. They were able to play games together over long distances and communicate with

one another via an audio interface. In reality, users can subscribe to an MMORPG (massively multiplayer online role-playing game) and play alongside thousands of other players at any time (Saito, et al., 2021).

Additionally, Social connections are central to our well-being. Humans have relied on one another since the beginning of time for survival, and there may be a greater desire for social interaction as a means of escaping the demands and complexities of the modern world. Having friends and family fulfills a natural human need to belong, to feel supported, valued, and socially connected to others. Connecting socially also provides other health and well-being benefits. Social connections can really help you live longer (National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, Division of Population Health, 2023).

Clearly, it impacts both the state of your physical and emotional wellness. Most people and individuals with stronger social relationships had a greater chance of surviving, which held for a variety of variables, such as age, sex, starting health, and reason for death. It can also decrease your risk of suicide: Several factors, according to the Centers for Disease Control, make persons more or less likely to commit suicide (National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, Division of Population Health, 2023).

Relationships can be a critical barrier in preventing suicidal thoughts and actions. The Centers for Disease Control (CDC) defines connectivity; one of these traits is described as "the degree to which a person or group is socially close, interrelated, or shares resources with other persons or groups." Therefore, according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, a five-tier model of human wants that is part of a psychological, motivational theory is frequently represented as tiers within a pyramid with hierarchical levels.

On the third of his pyramid, which starts from the bottom to the top of the hierarchy, the demands are physiological (food and clothing), safety (work security), love and belonging (friendship), esteem, and self-actualization. It was actually composed of the deficiencies and growth needs of an individual or this five-staged model can be separated into two categories: deficit and growth needs. The first four levels are commonly the lowest level is known as deficiency needs (D-needs), while the highest level is known as growth or being needs (B-needs). As Maslow stated in his pyramid, individuals must satisfy lower-level deficit needs before progressing on to meet higher-level growth requirements. Deficiency needs come from deprivation and are considered to motivate people when unsatisfied.

Similarly, the longer such requirements go unmet, the higher the incentive to meet them. For example, the longer a person is without much care and attention from their families and homes, the hungrier they need acceptance and approval from others and the society they belong to. They will become more eager to fill in that emptiness in them, just like what the researchers observed in most of the participants during their one-on-one, in-depth interviews.

They tend to have this emptiness and social deficiency from their loved ones and families. In the context of this study, the five specified participants were still at the 3rd stage at a level under deficiency needs, which is social needs or belongingness. Thus, DOTA gaming became their first option to meet those social deficiencies in them. For this reason, they consider this part of their daily routine, and most of their time is spent playing Defense of the Ancients online gaming.

Indeed, they counted the game as their escape to the real-world problematic scene in which they found it pleasurable fun as amusements and recreations that this game had actually brought to their lives. Upon playing DOTA, it is undeniable that players develop a sense of belongingness and connection. One of the main reasons why they developed a passion for DOTA games is the human connection they enable and achieve while playing the said online game. This became especially relevant when the pandemic hit the Philippines and all over the world. The feelings of isolation and loneliness are some of the critical negatives that the quarantine has brought upon us and our mental health; even more, people indulged in online games surrounding themselves, even in a digital medium, people with whom they have something in common have an excellent effect on their mental health.

. For this reason, It has also been observed that this method of meeting people is beneficial for persons who deal with social anxiety besides strengthening social connections, most participants confirmed that DOTA also served as their recreational therapy and coping mechanism. The advancement of technology has taken the world to a whole new experience and a totally different way of living and trends. Most of our young ones spend their leisure time playing video games as a pastime. Leisure is defined as time set aside for discretionary activities, such as recreation. One fundamental aspect of human nature is the "need to do something for recreation". Often for enjoyment, amusement, or pleasure, these are considered fun field experiences. It refers to all those activities that we choose to do to refresh our bodies and minds and make our leisure time more exciting and enjoyable. Examples of recreation and, at the same time, therapeutic activities are walking, swimming, meditation, reading, dancing, playing games, and browsing the internet. Besides, it became an amusement attraction that included several attractions, including water rides, mechanical rides, shows, theme exhibits, picnic grounds, and currently diverse games.

Such as DOTA. Video games have become a regular pastime and a well-known aspect of household culture thanks to their enormous global fan base, as well as their increased mobility thanks to smartphones. Gause stressed that gamers reported that the gameplay was pleasurable mainly due to the fact that it helped them alleviate stress; it became their outlet to escape their problems and challenges temporarily, participants confided. DOTA became their best option to overcome their social deficiency needs, and most of them considered it as their Recreational therapy in coping with the difficulties in their daily lives. (White, 2020).

Upon playing this game, they developed a sense of belongingness and connection to others. Thus, DOTA became their recreational

activity, and most of them are amused by its unique and special features aside from its good graphics.

Apparently, it has a considerable price pool, and it was so easy to play that it made the game more attractive to the participants. P1, P2, P3, and P5 also added that it helps them forget and escape their problems, and they enjoyed this game because it taught them strategies for how to develop teamwork and how to collaborate with teams, especially during their team fights. DOTA also brought them aptitude enrichment; video games are causally associated with an improvement in visual-spatial abilities, which are helpful in scientific technology and engineering (Agariadne, et al., 2023; Sedrick & Bonotan, 2019).

Thus, in this context, Complex games may lead to educational success by engaging players in problem-solving, critical thinking, and creativity in various fields. P1 & P2 stated that it improved their interpersonal skills like team communication, eye coordination, concentration, and mental alertness. At the same time, P3, P4, and P5 added that it developed their creativity, good mindset, critical thinking, and multitasking ability. According to Smith in his article entitled “Bad & Good Effects of Computer Games on Students,” in the midst of varying effects of video games (Smith, 2018).

Moreover, there are still researchers who studied how these electronic games can be harnessed for educational purposes, and this study reveals that playing DOTA requires strategy and critical thinking, considered higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), that is, higher than mere rote memorization. Higher-order thinking skills include critical thinking, analyzing, reasoning, and synthesizing.

Moreover, evaluating and creating. In this context, it improves interpersonal skills and develops team communication; it improves eye coordination, concentration, mental alertness, creativity, good mindset, critical thinking, various relevant strategies, and multitasking abilities. Which are common and predominant among participants of this study. Certainly, DOTA players as they played the game. Similarly, the researchers confirmed that, in some ways, it does develop learners' HOTS or higher-order thinking skills, especially if it is played in moderation (Smith, 2018; Sedrick & Bonotan, 2019; Agariadne, et al., 2023).

Videogames can power up from just merely fun to meaningful experiences. Swayne. In this context, participants admitted that they joined their friends in the play to exercise their creativity, imaginative and critical thinking, and multitasking abilities. Thus, it is evident that they often have all experienced hard and challenging times, and in order for them to escape this situation temporarily, they tend to choose Defense of the Ancients online gameplay for temporary amusement and recreation; in addition, “Online Gaming More Than Pastime for Some Gamers” stated that video gaming permits players to do different things or as their Recreational therapy that served as their way of coping up from their sadness, loneliness, Anxiety, and stress (Chitra, et al.,2023).

To such a degree, they do not know the fact that there are possible risks of overdoing the said online game on their well-being. Richard and Morison stressed that Media are physical forms that can stimulate and convey knowledge to be learned. DOTA is an online video game where strategy and critical thinking are essential skills that the player must possess; if the player aims to ace the game, he uses MMR or Making Rank as a determinant of the player’s skill and rank.

As the player continues to win battles, their MMR rank increases. Having a high MMR means that the player is adept at the game. This can be construed to mean that the player has an equally high aptitude for critical thinking and strategy.

Table 2 revealed that Dota created an adrenaline rush due to extreme happiness and excitement among participants. They felt thrilled and nervous, and they described that they were like on cloud nine while they were engaged in the game; they also confided that playing these games made them feel excited and usually became the source of their temporary relief and happiness, which they claimed their outlet for escaping the challenges and problems they currently have. According to P1, he felt like he was on cloud nine and that he felt extreme happiness while he played the game (Brennan, 2021).

Hence, Dan Brennan, MD, stressed that the reason you feel stronger during an adrenaline rush is because of a chemical reaction within you. Blood arteries constrict due to adrenaline, directing blood flow to the central muscle units. Your heart and muscles receive more blood when adrenaline is present. Adrenaline's effects might last for up to an hour after you have been removed from the stressful situation. Hormonal changes cause an adrenaline rush.

Basically, the excessive release of epinephrine can be harmful to our bodies. It gives us a good feeling that causes us to seek out another adrenaline rush; the negative impact of an Adrenaline rush on our health is the sudden onset of stress, and excess stress hormones released in our body can have adverse effects. The physical and emotional stress placed on our body and heart can be damaging to our heart. A condition known as a broken heart happens when our blood flow is reduced because of intense emotional distress (Brennan, 2021).

Likewise, P2 confirmed his Positive and Pleasant feelings of excitement and adrenaline rush, the sense of intense excitement or a stress hormone, and overactive adrenal glands; an adrenaline rush happens in a very stressful situation or due to Anxiety. Again, it is something great to feel, but in excess, it can be dangerous, too, for the body gradually recovers from the peak hormone rush following an adrenaline rush. . It means that their body was flooded with energy during the play, which is not normal if often felt by an individual because, if a person always felt this, it can cause serious health problems (Brennan,2021).

Similarly, P3 and P4 felt hyperactive and nervous. Frequently, hyperactivity is a sign of a medical or mental health issue. Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a primary ailment linked to hyperactivity when it is exhibited excessively. You become

impulsive, inattentive, and overactive when you have ADHD. It is usually diagnosed at a young age (Brennan, 2021).

Moreover, Online game the World Health Organization classifies addiction as a mental health condition. The participants in this study mentioned positive and pleasant feelings, P1, P2, P3, and P4 felt happy, joyful, good, proud, satisfied, and motivated. That is why they kept on playing this game, due to the pleasure they got, and it became their favorite hang-out or time activity to refrain from any negativities and burdens in their lives temporarily. They find it satisfying and amusing, but it also becomes intense for them, making them more active and comfortable interacting with their co-players or teammates because they cooperate in order to win the game; there were also corresponding negative and unpleasant feelings confided by the participants; for instance, P1 said that when asked what he felt when he lost the game (WHO, 2022).

However, he said that he felt disheartened and depressed; depression (major depressive disorder) is a prevalent and dangerous medical condition that has a detrimental impact on one's emotions, thoughts, and behavior. Depressive disorders result in depressed moods and a loss of interest in past interests. It can make it harder for you to operate at work and cause a range of mental and physical issues at school and home (Chitra et al., 2023; Dongil et al., 2022).

In this context, Depression symptoms include feeling down or depressed, losing interest in or enjoying once-enjoyed hobbies, experiencing changes in appetite, losing or gaining weight without dieting, having trouble falling asleep or sleeping too much, feeling more exhausted or losing energy, engaging in pointless physical exercise, slowed movements or speech; these actions are observable to the participants and also based on their responses during the one-on-one in-depth inter Continue playing games despite negative consequences such as obsession, obsession with Internet games, building up a tolerance, loss of interest in other life activities.

In such a way, Failure really does not feel good yet. We all need to accept this instead of regretting all the misfortunes that come our way. In particular, there are a number of things people can do to help reduce the symptoms of depression; regular exercise helps create positive feelings and improves sentiment. Maintaining a nutritious diet, getting regular restful sleep, and avoiding depressant substances and activities can also help reduce symptoms of depression P2 and P3 supported that they want to take revenge or rematch, especially if they lose the game (American Psychological Association, 2013).

On this note, there is a tendency or a big possibility that they become hooked on the said online game, for they cannot totally accept the fact of losing. However, some of them know how to carry and control the intensity of playing the game. According to P5, if he wins, he feels proud of himself, while if he loses, it is okay for him to lose, for it is part of the game, but the majority of them want to have revenge and rematch after losing the said game.

In this vein, psychological study into the influence of DOTA games on players began more than fifteen years ago, with studies devoted to determining the purported harmful impact of game playing. There are several public debates about what some see as the detrimental nature of gaming. A recent example of this is a BBC interview with Dr. Phil Zimbardo. Despite Dr. Andrew Przybylski's astute deconstruction and critique of Zimbardo's claims, prejudices against video gaming are often resistant to reevaluation. The APA recently revealed results from their Task Force on Violent Media in 2013, which claimed a 'consistent' relationship between aggression and playing violent video games (Zimbardo, 2015).

Actually, It should be noted that this report contributed to impeding advancement by reinvigorating long-standing opinions about the impacts of video games, despite subsequent research in numerous fields outlining the beneficial effects of playing video games. Parents play central roles in adolescents' socialization, behavioral development, and health, including the development of the internet, wherein excessive engagement creates an increased risk of IGD or Internet Gaming Disorder; there should be Parental Psychological control, controlling young adolescents' behavior by overly regulating their thoughts and feelings (Chitra, et al.,2023).

However, according to Adams, online games should be used for entertainment purposes where all fatigue and stress can be reduced or totally washed out by playing online games. In reality, the reverse happens: online games are played in excess, especially among some Senior high school learners, which leads them to be in the hooked state. On the other hand, The current phenomenon shows that Grade 12 Secondary learners of Fatima National High School are: (Kabir, 2020).

Constantly and continually hooked to Defense of the Ancients, which is widely known as DOTA, On the other hand, Adolescence is a transition period from childhood to adulthood associated with perceptions and stereotypes about deviations; there are many different harmful and unpleasant feelings that most of the participants have. Some deviations often start from the Online World, Ifdils, and Ardi; in this context, Trashtalks, Gambling, deceiving, and stealing are evident in some of the respondents/participants. Evidently, the most serious and so alarming effects of DOTA are with P1, who admitted that playing this game made him more aggressive.

Hence, to what extent did he commit a stealing crime against his neighbor? Later, he regretted the most because his credibility as a person was tainted and damaged just because of the DOTA game that he did not want to miss; he took a domestic chicken from his neighbor's house, and unfortunately, he was caught and then later reported to the barangay for the crime he committed Thus, this secondary learner is too young for all these scenes. They must be guided accordingly by their parents, teachers, and school heads where they are enrolled.

Consequently, this study sheds light on whom it may concern that can change and help solve this current situation, especially among these hooked learners. School heads and administrators, teachers' parents, and other concerns should not overlook or underestimate

the experiences of these DOTA-hooked players. This research aims to address and cater to the unique needs of this DOTA hooked learners in line with the mission and vision of the Department of Education to promote quality and equitable education for all and learners and enable a supportive environment for effective lifelong learning to happen.

Hence, DOTA undeniably created Positive and Pleasant feelings for the participants; all those positive feelings were outweighed by their harmful and unpleasant feelings, especially after the game or when they experienced loss in the game where they could feel sad, annoyed, disgusted, frustrated, and depressed. This study has some in common: Feeling bad, sad, frustrated, lonely, tired, hungry, unsatisfied or dissatisfied, bored, disappointed, weak, and jealous, which are alarming, especially if they don't have self-control because these emotions they can commit unexpected mistakes or harm to others if not adequately addressed by the concerned individuals.

It can extend their help to the advantage of this DOTA hooked learners, like guidance counselors, teachers, and even school administrators, based on the affliction and difficulties they experienced while being unaware of the adversities and damages it caused them for being hooked in DOTA. Table 3 exposed that The participants' lived experiences in the Defense of the ancients were actually alarming. Based on Table 3, most of them became aggressive, anti-social, loners, shy, and lost confidence to talk with other people, this is quite an alarming case.

As a result, most of them develop an inferiority complex or low self-esteem, which is "a fundamental sense of insufficiency and unease, resulting from actual or perceived physical or mental deficiencies, low self-esteem, the lack of confidence about who they are and what they can do, they often felt incompetent, unloved or inadequate most of the participants responded almost the same. P2 said that he lost his confidence in talking with others because of too much focus on the game (Dongil et al., 2022).

Definitely, it does destroy his social life. Most of them confirmed that they would rather be alone than be with someone who can keep them from playing this game; there are also health Risks or Physical and Mental health deficiencies that were affected while being so hooked on DOTA gaming. P1 develop insomnia due to lack of sleep, and most of them also confirmed that they often sleep late and sometimes at dawn; they became forgetful, unable to focus, develop headaches, and tiresome due to lack of physical exercise and because of overdoing the play they lost their healthy diet and appetite that caused them stomach ache and irritability. Most of them mentioned the same health problems that are so dangerous, especially to their immune system (Clark et al., 2022; Purwaningsih et al., 2021).

Thus, Inadequate sleep can significantly impair our immune system, which is essential for fending off diseases and, infections, suicide. The Centers for Disease Control state that a number of factors Many students report that their sleep is disrupted by their obsession with Dota, which haunts and bothers them even during the night. They often find themselves dreaming about in-game clashes and team fights, making it difficult to rest properly.

Overall, this constant mental engagement with the game contributes to ongoing exhaustion and a lack of drive to wake up early for school. Additionally, the time spent playing Dota can result in the neglect of other pursuits, like eating, as the immediate satisfaction from the game takes precedence over basic needs

Dota has a significant impact on the lifestyles of students who are hooked to the game. It may have some positive aspects, but it primarily affects the mind and alters the way students think. It weakens the body system. The game does not promote Discipline or moral values (Chitra, et al., 2023).

For instance, P5 noted that a lack of self-control while playing led to stress, Anxiety, and mental blocks, which can be pretty harmful. Anxiety, characterized by feelings of worry, dread, and uneasiness, manifested in physical symptoms such as profuse sweating, restlessness, agitation, and an elevated heart rate; these reactions can be a normal response to stress, but their intensity and frequency can be concerning (Chitra, et al., 2023).

As a result, individuals often experience Anxiety when confronted with complex challenges at work or before taking tests, which can significantly affect their academic performance. Symptoms associated with this Anxiety can interfere with daily activities, work performance, schoolwork, and relationships with family and friends (Can & Tekkurşun, 2020; Saito, et al., 2021; Sarper Kahveci, 2020). While Some studies suggest that high involvement in video games may exacerbate these issues, leading to problems like time management difficulties, sleep deprivation, weight gain, obesity, physical complaints (e.g., eye strain, backache), increased aggressive behavior, impulsive decision-making, and addiction (Can & Tekkurşun, 2020; Saito, et al., 2021; Sarper Kahveci, 2020).

At some point, this research study exposed some Effects of DOTA on the Academic Performance of the participants. P1 confirms that he no longer prioritizes his studies because he is too focused on the game, just like P2 said; he has no time to study anymore because he's too focused on the said DOTA game. While P3 stated that he became forgetful and couldn't get good grades at school and did not do his assignments, P4 and P5 added that they get lower grades and can't focus in School, like always forgetting their daily school activities and plans. (Sugaya, et al., 2019; Dongil, et al., 2022).

Conclusion

However, online games should be used for entertainment purposes where all fatigue and stress can be reduced or totally washed out by playing online games; in reality, the reverse happens: online games are played in excess, especially among some Senior high school

learners, which leads them to be hooked state; the current phenomenon shows that Grade 12 Secondary learners of Fatima National High School are constantly and continually connected to Defense of the Ancients widely known as DOTA. There were many negative and unpleasant feelings that most of the participants in this study had something in common.

For instance, Feeling bad, sad, frustrated, lonely, tired, hungry, unsatisfied or dissatisfied, disgusted, bored, disappointed, weak, and jealous, which are alarming. Especially if they do not have the self-control to handle these various emotions. As a result, they can commit unexpected mistakes or harm to others if not adequately addressed by the concerned individuals who can extend their help to the advantage of these hooked learners, like guidance counselors, teachers, and even school administrators. Furthermore, based on the affliction and difficulties they experienced while being unaware of the adversities and damages it caused them for being hooked in DOTA.

Evidently, This research aims to address and cater to the unique needs of this DOTA hooked learners in line with the mission and vision of the Department of Education to promote quality and equitable education for all to nurture learners and enable a supportive environment for effective learning to happen by means of a favorable partnership between the School School and the community particularly with parents and other stakeholders in order to yield beautiful harvest by way of establishing a conducive learning atmosphere in the School School and an orderly and civic-minded citizenry in the community for “it takes a village to raise a child.

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